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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

THE KNIGHTS OF THE SIBYL - GUERRINO THE WRETCH AND HIS FOREFATHERS: HUON D'AUVERGNE¹

1. "Huon d'Auvergne" and its connection to the legend of the Apennine Sibyl

As considered in a previous paper, we are in search of clues which may guide scholars towards an improved understanding of the literary sources used by Andrea da Barberino in his chivalric romance "Guerrino the Wretch", and by Antoine de La Sale in his "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl".

Where did the two listed authors get specific episodes from? Is there any literary ancestor of such peculiar themes as the revolving metal doors featured in the "Paradise", or the journey to Rome in search of an absolution to be bestowed by the Pope, as found in "Guerrino", "The Paradise" and even "Tannhäuser"?

We saw that such an ancestor is partly to be retrieved in "Huon of Bordeaux", a thirteenth-century epic poem written in French: a poem including specific episodes as found in the works written one hundred fifty years later by the above writers, Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de La Sale.

However, this progenitor is not the one and only.

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Now we are going to turn our attention to another "Huon": this time we will consider "Huon d'Auvergne", another chivalric poem belonging to an ancient French-Italian tradition, for which four surviving manuscripts (Berlin, Turin, Padua, Bologna) dating between 1341 and 1441 provide a highly interesting witness to an ancestry that appears to be rooted in a past that seems to come down straight from earlier centuries.

Huon d'Auvergne - just like his namesake Huon of Bordeaux, Guerrino the Wretch and the Antoine de La Sale's German nobleman - is a knight and a member of the aristocracy. He is the main character of a romance which features epic deeds of loyalty and betrayal, travels in far-away countries and exploration of magical lands. As Huon from Bordeaux and Guerrino, this second Huon also lives in the age of Emperor Charlemagne and his lineage.

Has "Huon d'Auvergne" anything to do with the Apennine Sibyl's literary legend and lore?

The answer is actually yes. This valiant knight experiences a number of adventures which seem to have a close connection to the magical world of the Apennine Sibyl as we know it from other literary works, though no direct reference to the sibilline legend is present in "Huon d'Auvergne".

A most striking episode is contained in Manuscript n. 32 preserved at the Library of the Episcopal Theological School in Padua (Italy). In the folium no. 59, Huon d'Auvergne is travelling near the Tigris river. And there he meets three handsome damsels:

«three damsels [...] Each one of them was remarkably handsome - their eyes sparkling and their cheeks most white - and as red as fresh roses - their slender arms on their beautiful shoulders - their breasts dancing before them»

[in the original French-Italian text: «tre damissele [...] De gran beleça fo çascuna d'eles - Li so ochi à vari e blanche lor maseles - Color vermeio como ruoxe noveles - Sulle spale pendeano lor dreçe beles - Davanti lo sso peti ponceano le so mameles»].

The scene is significantly similar to that depicted in Andrea da Barberino's "Guerrino the Wretch", when the main character, in the hidden recesses of the Sibyl's cave, knocks at a door flanked by two sculpted demons. The door opens, and three damsels appear before the brave knight:

«the three damsels were so handsome and perfectly shaped that no tongue will ever be able to depict their beauty» [in the original Italian text: «queste erano tre damigelle tanto polite e belle che lingua mai non lo potrebe dire tanto era la loro belezza»].

Fig. 1 - A page from one of the surviving manuscripts containing "Huon d'Auvergne", preserved at the Library of the Episcopal Theological School in Padua (Italy)

Then Guerrino meets the Sibyl, and she «shows him her own fairness and her white flesh, with her breasts which looked like polished ivory» [in the original Italian text: «mostrandoli la sua bellezza e le sue bianche carne e le mamelle che pareano proprio che fossero da volio»].

Just a typical chivalric episode, with beautiful ladies who lure the unblemished knights into sin, and with no relation at all with the Sibyl's legend?

We don't think so. Because in the excerpt from "Huon d'Auvergne" we find a few additional lines that are utterly astonishing. When Huon asks the ladies where they are from, the answer provided by the pretty damsels is as follows:

«You must be aware that our master
is a dame from the mountain.
Neither Medea nor Helen were so fair,
and no other woman was so wise in Britain;
She is proficient in black arts,
more than all the scholars in Toledo and Spain»

[in the original French-Italian text:
«Tu dé saver ch'el nostro capetaïne
È una dame de çà da la montagne.
No fo si bela Medea ni Helaine,
Nian si savia fui in Bertagne;
De negromencia ella è sovraïne,
Plui che no sé sença ingagne
Tuti li maistri de Toleta ni de Spagne»].

And they add: «she knows the language of necromancy - if you know how to ask and tell her [...] - you will be able to know how to go to Mount Hell»
[in the original French-Italian text: «de negromançia sa tuto lo latin - Se tu te saveré domandar e contar a lei ben vexin [...] - E può saver da lie tuto lo train - Como tu anderé al munte inferin»].

So a "dame from the mountain" rules over a court of handsome ladies and delivers oracular responses to her visitors: it seems to hear an echo, faint as it may be, of the Sibyl residing under the Apennine mountains. And the dame is called «savìa» (wise): the very same Italian word used by Andrea da Barberino to define the Sibyl throughout his romance!

Does the Apennine Sibyl described in works such as "Guerrino the Wretch" and "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl" originate from an ancient model of fairy dame included in an earlier chivalric poem, "Huon d'Auvergne"?

Before providing an answer, let's continue with our insight into "Huon": we will find many other - astounding - correspondences.

2. Huon's enchanted court and magical queen

Let's continue to find footprints of the legend of the Apennine Sibyl in "Huon d'Auvergne", an epic poem which includes episodes that seem to be the ancestors of narrative sequences encountered in the sibilline literature ("Guerrino the Wretch", "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl").

We saw that the main character, Huon d'Auvergne, runs into three damsels and an enchanted court, subject to the rule of a most beautiful lady who features many traits in common with the Sibyl.

Just like Guerrino the Wretch, Huon follows the damsels to meet the handsome queen, but - as with the Sibyl's subterranean court - an evil spell is working on the brave hero: «the Devil was using all his powers - to lead him into wicked straits» [«che llo diavollo adoverave la sso possança - de condurlo a malvasse sentança»]. The spell of the magnificent castle he is led into is so powerful that Huon thinks to himself that «I would never go back to my Alvernia» («mai non curerav'io in Alvernia torner»).

That's exactly the same magical spell that locked the visiting knights forever within the enchanted kingdom of the Apennine Sibyl.

When Huon is admitted to the presence of the queen («la raina»), his eyes behold a most beautiful woman; yet our valiant knight «knows for certain that her fairness was fake and illusory» («sapié per certaine - che sso belleça era falssa e vaine»). The above words remind to us the entreaty raised by Guerrino in his heart when he was before the Queen Sibyl and her divine beauty: «he said for three times 'Jesu Christ from Nazareth free my soul from such beguilements'» («disse tre volte Iesu christo nazareno libera me da questi incantamenti»).

In "Huon d'Auvergne", the queen will try to lure Huon into sin - the same luxurious sin as offered by the Apennine Sibyl to her visitors: and Huon will raise the very same cry - «come to my aid, Jesus from Nazareth» [«Secori lo to servo, naçareno Jexhu»] - as Guerrino the Wretch will utter in despair in an identical occurrence in Andrea da Barberino's romance: «Jesus Christ from Nazareth save my soul» [«Iesu christo nazareno fame salvo»].

Fig. 2 - A fine miniature depicting a knight and a queen, from a manuscript containing the romance "Yvain"

At last, both Huon and Guerrino actually succeed in preserving their own purity: they resist the enticements presented to them by their ghastly queens, so that all enchantments disappear and they can leave the magical kingdoms unblemished.

Huon's queen and the Apennine Sibyl - both coming from the mountains, skilled in necromancy, ruling a splendid yet illusory court, described as wise and providing oracular responses, craving for the souls of visitors, luring people into sin: is the Sibyl we know from Andrea da Barberino's and Antoine de La Sale's works descending from a earlier model, already

contained in "Huon d'Auvergne" epic romance (which is in turn based on an even earlier oral tradition)?

The answer is... perhaps! But, before we provide a more definite response, let's have a look at further correspondences between "Huon" and his later offsprings.

Because there are actually further correspondences between "Huon d'Auvergne" and the literary works pertaining to the Apennine Sibyl. We will highlight them in our next post.

3. A most narrow bridge and an ever-slammimg metal gate

"Guerrino the Wretch" and "The Paradis of Queen Sibyl": two most renowned fifteenth-century works which are the cornerstones of the legend of the Apennine Sibyl. Do such books originate from earlier works?

Apparently, they have no ancestor: they seem to have popped up from a literary void. But this is not true: this void is full of elusive clues, contained in a number of earlier epic poems. We saw that "Huon of Bordeaux", dating back to the thirteenth century, includes narrative themes that are also retrieved in the later sibilline literature.

And another Huon, namely "Huon d'Auvergne", an epic set down on fourteenth-century manuscripts but descending from earlier oral traditions, seems to portray an evil queen featuring the same characters as the Apennine Sibyl.

But let's go further ahead. If we continue our perusal of "Huon d'Auvergne" we find out other astounding correspondences with the Sibyl's legend.

In the ancient epic, the brave knight Huon d'Auvergne sets off in a supernatural travel into Hell, the way Dante Alighieri had described in his "Divine Comedy". During his journey, beyond the Limbo and a castle containing the souls of illustrious pagans, Huon stumbles upon something we know already from the Sibyl's legend: an unfathomable abyss, and a very special bridge crossing it.

«There he can see no bridge made of wood or stone,
but only a plank was there to cross.
I will tell you how cruel was that bridge:
Its top side is as sharp as an arrow
And it cleaves more easily than a sword;
Nobody can get through that waters
but for that bridge I am telling you about.
Hun looked at it and began to weep,
[...] first he signed himself with the cross,
then they ventured across the bridge with small steps,
so that they safely reached the far edge.»

[in the original French-Italian text at Folium 101 recto in the Padua manuscript:

«No lli vete ponte de legname ni de piere,
Ma un stangon li vè desovra stere.
La crudelitade del ponte ve voio contere:
Desovra è agudo como quarel d'açere
E pluy ca spada ello taia volentiere,
E algun non può oltra quela aqua paxere
Se no per quel ponte ch'io vo contere.
Ugo lo guarda, molto prexe a llarmoiere,
[...] primamente se fè la croxe al vis,
Po se meteno su per lo ponte a pas petis,
Tanto che sono oltro el pont sulla ris.»]

The bridge on the abyss: a magical, frightfully narrow path which lets the sinner fall down as he treads on it, and yet allowing the passage of the faithful, its narrowness being just an illusion, its width broadening as the true believer in God accepts its challenge.

The very same bridge we find in Antoine de La Sale's "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl", deep within Mount Sibyl and the Sibyl's cave:

«Then you find a bridge, made of some unknown material, but it is said to be less than a single foot wide and it seems to be extending far ahead. Below the bridge, a ghastly, precipitating abyss [...] Yet as soon as you put both feet on the bridge, it becomes large enough; and the more you step ahead,

the more it widens and the abyss becomes shallower» [in the original French text: «Lors trouve-l'on un pont, que on ne scet de quoy il est, mais est advis qu'il n'est mie un pied de large et semble estre moult long. Dessoubz ce pont, a très grant et hydeux abisme de parfondeur [...] Mais aussitost que on a les deux pieds sur le pont, il est assez large; et tant va on plus avant et plus est large et moins creux»].

A bridge - we note incidentally - that comes down from an even earlier tradition, lost in the mist of the Middle Ages, as we will detail in a subsequent article.

That's enough? Not at all.

Because, just a few folia ahead in the Padoa manuscript, when Huon arrives to the castle of Lucifer, we find another striking occurrence, already found in Antoine de la Sale:

«A lofty palace, with a tower standing before it,
Not made of stone as towers are used to be made;
That is made of metal, and tempered iron;
High walls are around the palace,
A front gate guarded by two lions,
And the gate is such
That as soon as it is swung open,
No blade is as sharp as the gate itself,
the doors cutting easily and sweetly;
they just keep on opening up and shutting close».

[in the original French-Italian text at Folia 105 verso and 106 recto]:

«Alto è el pallaço, una tore davanti li à,
No è de piere como le tore se fa,
Ançy è d'açalle e de fero tenperà;
Alti son li muri ch'el palaço cricundà,
Davanti à una porta che do lion guardà,
E quele porte tal natura si à
Si tosto como elle averte incontenente se serà,
El non è raxori tanto taienti e filà
Che taia cossì soave como quele porte fa;
De serar e de avre alltro elle non fa».]

Amazingly enough, this is just the metal device lashing «throughout summers and winters» («batent et yver et esté») we already encountered in "Huon of Bordeaux", another chivalric poem, and in de La Sale's "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl", with its metal doors «slamming day and night without rest» («qui jour et nuyt et sans ceser battent, cloant et ouvrant»)! Another ancient narrative belonging to an old Middle Age tradition.

So it appears clear to us that specific links exist between "Huon d'Auvergne" and the sibilline literary lore: the tale about the Apennine Sibyl seems to have inherited specific attributes that once belonged to the dens of earlier "villains" appearing in older chivalric poems.

Fig. 3 - Front pages of a nineteenth-century edition of "Ugone d'Avernia" and an earlier edition of "Guerrino the Wretch"

Did people such as Antoine de La Sale and Andrea da Barberino know of those older poems?

The answer is yes. De La Sale was a man of letter and a courtier. Andrea da Barberino did something even more conclusive: at the end of the fourteenth century he wrote an Italian translation of "Huon d'Auvergne": a romance whose title is "Ugone d'Avernia", a sort of "Guerrino the Wretch" containing the Huon's deeds and adventures expanded from the original manuscripts of "Huon d'Auvergne".

Therefore, we can state that the Apennine Sibyl's legendary lore contains literary topics that are drawn from earlier chivalric works: these topics are assigned by illustrious men of letters (Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de La Sale) to a specific place and cavern located on a remote peak of the Apennines, which, for some reasons, already used to attract visitors interested in necromancy and concealed magical kingdoms.

All that sounds as an astoundingly interesting area for further research.

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